

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No.: B040
Date: 20 Aug 2004
Take Off 13:10:02
Landing: 17:44:27
Flight Time 4h34m25

Trials Instructions: Pre-ADRIEX shakedown flight to test ADRIEX instrumentation with particular reference to the SWS and BBR instruments.

Operating Area: High altitude flying over the SW approaches above all low-level cloud and free from any cirrus cloud. London/Scottish FIR. Anticipated operating area:- north of 56N, east of 2W.

POB	Position	Name	Institute
1	Captain	Alan Foster	Directflight
2	Co-pilot	Alan Roberts	Directflight
3	Mission Scientist 1	Jim Haywood	Met Office
4	Flight Manager	Maureen Smith	FAAM
5	CCN	Stuart Heath	FAAM
6	CVI	Paul James	FAAM
7	Cloud Physics	Martyn Pickering	Met Office
8	SWS	Ian Rule	Met Office
9	SWS	Andy Wilson	Met Office
10	ARIES	Alan Vance	Met Office
11	ARIES	Stuart Rodgers	Met Office
12	FWVS	Joss Kent	Met Office
13	FWVS	James Bowles	Met Office
14		Jim McQuaid	Leeds University
15	VACC	Barbara Brooks	Leeds University
16	CCM	Sue Angold	Directflight
17			
18			
19			

Flight Track:

B040 Track 20-AUG-04

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No B040
 Date: 20/07/04
 Project: Pre-ADRIEX test
 Location:

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
----	----	-----	-----	---	-----
131002		T/O	2.0 kft	018	From Cranfield
135410	135613	Run 1	30.0 kft	041	In clear air
135620	140333	Profile 1	31.0 - 32.0 kft	001	
140716	142517	Run 2	32.0 kft	045	Down Sun
140749		Neph	32.0 kft	045	Zero Cal
142805	143311	Run 3.1	32.0 kft	309	Box Pattern
143606	150111	Run 3.2	32.0 kft	231	Across Sun
150311	150840	Run 3.3	32.0 kft	144	Into Sun
151023	152902	Run 3.4	32.0 kft	058	Down Sun
153201	154003	Profile 2	32.0 - 25.0 kft	248	1000ft/min
154224	154522	Orbit 1	25.1 - 25.0 kft	312	30deg right bank
154523	154824	Orbit 2	25.0 - 25.1 kft	311	
154824	155129	Orbit 3	25.1 kft	313	
155129	155430	Orbit 4	25.1 - 25.0 kft	316	
155508	155646	Orbit 5	25.0 kft	074	45deg right bank,060
155653	155819	Orbit 6	25.1 - 25.0 kft	085	
155819	160002	Orbit 7	25.0 - 25.1 kft	028	
160002	160143	Orbit 8	25.1 - 25.0 kft	024	
160425	161332	Profile 3	25.1 - 32.0 kft	253	1000ft/min
161344	161733	Run 4	32.0 kft	252	Into Sun
161915	162415	Run 4.2	32.0 kft	165	Across Sun
162547	162948	Run 4.3	32.1 - 32.0 kft	080	Down Sun
163128	163532	Run 4.4	32.0 kft	347	Across Sun
163830	171435	Run 5	32.0 kft	194	Towards Cranfield
174427		Land	0.60 kft	047	At Cranfield

B040 Track 20-AUG-04

FAAM Sortie Brief

Pre-ADRIEX shakedown flight

Flight No: B040

Date 20 August 2004

Trial Objectives:

To test the ADRIEX instrumentation with particular reference to the SWS and BBR instruments.

Location:

High altitude flying off the Eastern coast of Scotland above all low-level cloud and free from any cirrus cloud. London/Scottish FIR. Anticipated operating area:- north of 56N, and east of 2W.

Weather:

Free from high-level cirrus cloud.

1. Flight Pattern:

2. Take off from Cranfield airport at 12:00GMT.
3. Transit to North Sea [20mins]
4. Perform profile ascent towards the operating area at 1000ft/minute to FL300 [40mins].
5. Straight and Level Run at FL300 to pre-defined position in the operating area [60mins].
6. Perform a run of 20-minutes duration down-sun (aircraft scientist will advise of the true heading) [80mins].
7. Perform a box-pattern consisting of 5-minute run across sun, 5-minutes into sun, 5-minutes across sun, and 5-minutes down-sun [110mins].
8. Perform a set of 4 complete orbits with an angle of bank close to that of the solar zenith angle (aircraft scientist will advise of the bank angle) [120mins].
9. Reposition [135mins].
10. Repeat 6, 8, and 9 as time allows [240mins].
11. Recover to Cranfield [300mins].

Sortie Debrief

Flight Number: B040

Sortie Objectives: Pre-ADRIEX shakedown, plus SWS initial flight

Operating area: To the East of Scotland.

Weather: An occluded front over the central UK with embedded Cb. Free from cirrus to the north of the occlusion. Broken Cu at low level.

Flight Patterns:

Take off at approximately 13:10Z from Cranfield. Held in seats because of heavy Cb activity in the area around Cranfield and further north. Tops of cloud at about ~FL220. Cloud physics hard disc failure during some turbulence – related? We then performed a run at FL300 during which there was still abt of Ci about above the aircraft. Profile ascent to FL320. The remainder of the flight was performed at FL320 (two box-patterns), except for a series of 4-orbits at 30° and a series of 4-orbits at 45°, both series being performed at FL250 during which SWS was set at 6° forwards facing (to counter the pitch angle of the aircraft).

Summary:

A successful test flight for the SWS instrument. SWS performed well – it was possible to locate the solar disc in both fore and aft positions for solar zenith angles. Clipped the wing at 55° solar zenith angle, and the tail at approximately 60° solar zenith angle. Neutral density filters 2+1 stopped module 1 from saturating when looking at the sun.

Problems:

ARIES failed early in the flight and did not operate after this failure.
PCASP channel 1 noisy on wing-mounted PCASP and CVI.
O3 reading 11ppbv throughout the flight
CNC needs fitting
Filter pump switch needs replacing
CCNC Peltier cooler problem
Total Water Content – failure half way through the flight
Upper Red BBR noisy for parts of the flight
Intercom on SWS not working properly
VACC pump needs beefing up as back-flow is a problem

Aircraft Scientist
Flight Manager's In-Flight Log

Flight No B.046..... Date20/August 2004..... Page1... of4...

Video Tapes	GPS	INU	DRS <input type="checkbox"/>
V8			
No.	Lat		HORACE <input type="checkbox"/>
Ends	Long		
FFC / RFC / DFC / UFC	Time		SATCOM <input type="checkbox"/>
	Status		

GMT	EVM	Height	QNH	Hdg	TAT	DP	DI	Wind/ Sea st.
13:10					Take-off		Htr	
13:53:54		FL156			Still in cloud tops			continuous climbing to FL200.
13:56:28		FL200			Still in cloud tops climbing to FL240.			
					(top of Ci) at Ci still heavy at FL210.			
					Tops of Ci at			
					Cloud physics hard disk failure.			
13:46:29		FL264			Still lots of Ci above.			
13:52:07		FL300						
13:54:10	SR1	FL300		040	Run at FL300 - still abt of			
13:56:13	ER1	FL300		038	Ci above. Broken Cu below.			
13:56:13	St P1	FL300 ↑						
14:07:16	St R2			048	Down - sun FL320 (20 mins)			
					SWS saturates in solar module (when looking at sun)			
14:17:30					BBRs → upper cl			600 Wm ⁻²
					upper red			335
					lower cl			216
					lower red			84
					Completely clear above for lots of this run.			
					Maximum filter in → saturation			
					SWS reports icing at -50°C still occurs.			
14:25:17	ER2	FL320 →		048	Right hand turns into			
14:28:05	SR3				Cross sun run sun off left			
					ARRIS confirms no work in this flight			

Flight Manager's In-Flight Log

Flight No B...040

Date20/08/04.....

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Video Tapes
V8
No. Ends FFC / RFC / DFC / UFC

	GPS	INU
Lat		
Long		
Time		
Status		

DRS	<input type="checkbox"/>
HORACE	<input type="checkbox"/>
SATCOM	<input type="checkbox"/>

GMT	EVM	Height	QNH	Hdg	TAT	DP	DI Htr	Wind/ Sea st.
								BBRs showing significantly lower readings
								UClr 468 Wm ⁻²
								URed 279 Wm ⁻²
								LClr 201 Wm ⁻²
								LRed 78 Wm ⁻²
14:33:11	ER3-1	FL320 →				into-sun run		
14:36:06	SR3-2	FL320 →		231		ND 2 filter	→	module 1 no saturation module 2 saturation
						BBRs		UClr 472 Wm ⁻²
								URed 261 Wm ⁻²
								LClr 251 Wm ⁻²
								LRed 96 Wm ⁻²
								Upper Red showing some switching oscillation (printed out)
								Extending run to 25 mins to get out of Storage airspace.
								Free from Ci above / Cu below
								55.6° SZA
								6° pitch
								SW3 clipping the wing.
15:01:11	ER3-2	FL320 →						
15:03:11	SR3-3			143		Cross sun run.		
						BBRs		UClr 498 Wm ⁻²
								URed 282 Wm ⁻²
								LClr 98 Wm ⁻²
								LRed 33 Wm ⁻²
								higher readings than into sun run.
								No Ci

Flight Manager's In-Flight Log

Flight No B...040

Date20/08/04.....

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Video Tapes
V8
No.
Ends
FFC / RFC / DFC / UFC

	GPS	INU
Lat		
Long		
Time		
Status		

DRS	<input type="checkbox"/>
HORACE	<input type="checkbox"/>
SATCOM	<input type="checkbox"/>

FAAM © 2004

GMT	EVM	Height	QNH	Hdg	TAT	DP	DI Htr	Wind/ Sea st.
15:07:59								No Ci, scattered small Cu
15:08:40	End R33	FL320 [→]						below.
15:10:23	St R34	FL320 [→]						Down-sun
								Ideal conditions above clouds
								- no Ci. Scattered broken Cu.
								SWS - seems to be behaving
								very well 52° indicated
								by Ion & 52° on HORACE!!!
								2D + 1D seems only to
								saturate at the top.
15:29:02	E3.4	FL320						End run - turn to
								reciprocal heading.
15:32:01	Start P2	FL320 [↓]						Profile descent at 1000ft/min
15:40:03	End P2	FL250						
15:42:24	O1			315				30° banked orbits
15:45:23	E01/st02			at start				52° 61.88°
15:48:24	E02/st03							Some glitches with LW
15:51:29	E03/st04							Good conditions - no Ci.
15:54:30	E04-							Broken Cu below
								Total water probe
								problem - looks like
								DLU problem
15:55:04	St05	FL250		060				45° banked orbits
15:56:46	E05/st06	"						Good - no Ci
15:58:19	E06/st07	"						Low level Sc/Cu
16:01:43	E07/st08	"						"
16:04:25	St P3	FL250 [↑]						Profile ascent at 1000ft/min
								-46C at FL300
16:13:32	End P3	FL320 [→]						Start Run into-sun
		St R4						

~~CO.~~
NOx
SO2

Box pattern

Flight Manager's In-Flight Log

Flight No B.040

Date 20/08/04

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Video Tapes	GPS	INU	DRS <input type="checkbox"/>	
V8			HORACE <input type="checkbox"/>	
No.				SATCOM <input type="checkbox"/>
Ends FFC / RFC / DFC / UFC				
Lat				
Long				
Time				
Status				

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GMT	EVM	Height	QNH	Hdg	TAT	DP	DI Htr	Wind/ Sea st.
16:17:33		FL320		251T	Into-sun run			
16:17:33	EndR4.1							No Ci - broken Cu below
16:19:15	St R4.2	FL320						CVI & PCASP both showing. Cross sun noise on CnL. SWS zenith
								Crystal clear above
								4/8 Cu below. Sun RHS.
16:24:15	EndR4.2	FL320						
16:25:47	St R4.3	FL320		76T				Looking at sun glint.
16:29:48	EndR4.3	FL320						No saturation (no filters)
16:31:28	St R4.4	FL320						Cross-sun run. Sun on LHS. SWS nadir.
								4/8 Cu below.
16:35:32	EndR4.4							Clear above.
16:38:30	St R5	FL320						Start run 4/8 Cu below
								no Ci.
16:48:00								bubbly @ surface ^{3/8} clear ahead/around
10:50:00								Some Cirrus ahead ~50 km
10:58:30								approaching Cirrus expansive sheet with wisps under already will enter soon
18:02:30								entering cloud layer. (fast) very thin wall of cloud out & within 60 seconds just skimming along the top
17:13								out of clouds ^{3/8} Cu below
17:14:35	EndR5	FL320						descending to FL200
								ETA so clear above
17:21:40								Just above top of main cloud layer
17:23:00		FL200						into cloud tops only just, bouncing gently.
17:28:00								Large C0 to LHS ~50 miles.

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. B040

Date: 20/8/04

Operator: MAP

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G.M.T. DRS Time	PCASP		FSSP	SID1	2D2-C			2D2-P			Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block Transfer	Particle Count	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m3	Max Size	Habit	
13:54:10	Noise		Disk failure	20							Start Run 1 @ FL300
13:55:00											
13:56:13											End of Run 1
14:00:00											Start Run 2.1 @ FL320
14:07:16											
14:08:00											
14:10:00											
14:12:00											
14:14:00											
14:16:00											
14:18:00											
14:20:00											
14:22:00											
14:25:17											End of Run
14:28:05											Start Run 3.1 @ FL320
14:29:00											
14:31:00											
14:33:00											End of Run
14:33:11											
14:36:06											Start Run 3.2 @ FL320
14:37:00											
14:39:00											
14:41:00											
14:43:00											
14:45:00											
14:47:00											
14:49:00											
14:51:00											
14:53:00											
14:55:00											
14:57:00											
14:59:00											

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. B040

Date: 20/8/04

Operator: MAP

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G.M.T. DRS Time	PCASP		FSSP	SID1	2D2-C			2D2-P			Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block Transfer	Particle Count	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m3	Max Size	Habit	
15:01:11											End of Run 3.2
15:03:35											Start Run 3.3 @ FL320
15:04:00											
15:06:00											
15:08:00											
15:08:40											End of Run 3.3
15:10:23											
15:11:00											
15:13:00											
15:15:00											
15:17:00											
15:19:00											
15:21:00											
15:23:00											
15:25:00											
15:27:00											
15:29:00											
15:29:02											End of Run 3.4
15:32:01											Start profile 2 from FL320
15:33:30											FL310
15:34:32											FL300
15:35:31											FL290
15:36:33											FL280
15:37:40				10							FL270
15:38:54											FL260
15:40:03											End of Profile 2 @ FL250
15:42:24											Start Orbits @ FL250
15:43:00											
15:54:10											End of Orbits
15:55:04											Start Orbits @ FL250
15:56:00											
16:01:43											End of Orbits

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. B040

Date: 20/8/04

Operator: MAP

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G.M.T. DRS Time	PCASP		FSSP	SID1	2D2-C			2D2-P			Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block Transfer	Particle Count	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m3	Max Size	Habit	
16:04:28											Start Profile 3 from FL250
16:05:20											FL260
16:06:01											FL270
16:07:25											FL280
16:08:50											FL290
16:10:36											FL300
16:11:40											FL310
16:13:33											End of P3 Start Run 4.1 @ FL320
16:14:00											
16:16:00											
16:17:35											End of Run 4.1
16:19:15											Start Run 4.2 @ FL320
16:20:00											
16:22:00											
16:24:00											
16:24:15											End of Run 4.2
16:25:47											Start Run 4.3 @ FL320
16:26:00											
16:28:00											
16:29:48											End of Run 4.3
16:31:35											Start Run 4.4 @ FL320
16:32:00											
16:34:00											
16:35:10											End of Run 4.4
16:38:30											Start Run 5 @ FL320
16:40:00											
16:50:00											
17:00:00											
17:10:00											
17:14:35											End of Run 5
PCASP CH1,2,3 Noisy. SEADAS Tape Time offset = 0											

Shortwave Spectrometer (specky) Flight log

Flight Number B040

Date 20/8/04

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Times
LOCAL

NIR 003803

VIS 27581

A=Z+1

[SCAN ANGLE]

Start Time	Run	Data File	Para File	Dark File	VIS Integ Time / (avgs)	NIR Integ Time / (avgs)	Cycle Time	Number of Cycles	Height	Comments
1305 L				✓						
1309 L	✓									START RECORDING
1350 L								90A		STOP RECORDING
1410 L										take off
1407 L										video record start
1421:26								0°		start recording
142850								10F		clear window
143030								0°		
143245								180°		
144630 L								0°		
145410 L								0°		start run 1 FL300
145613 L								0°		interrupt run 1
145910 L								180°		
150635								50:33°		DB Run down Sun 50:33 A
150915								0°		insert filters
152020								0°	Filters fitted	Vis ND2.0 number 1 NIR ND2.0 2
152020								53:5°		
152517										end run 2
152805					FL320			0°		start run 3.1
153311										end run 3.1
153606										start run 3.2
160111										end run 2
160311				into Sun						start run 3.3
160430								0°		Additional ND1 filter
160805								180°		Vis 2 NIR 1 fitted
160840								180°		end run 3.3
161023								52°		run down Sun 3.4
162902								52°		end 3.4
1										remove all filters & profile to F1250
164023										end profile
164204						F1250		6°F		start ORB+1

Shortwave Spectrometer (specky) Flight log

Flight Number B040.....

Date 20/8/04.....

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Times Local (Z+1)

(Scan angle)

Start Time	Run	Data File	Para File	Dark File	VIS Integ Time / (avgs)	NIR Integ Time / (avgs)	Cycle Time	Number of Cycles	Height	Comments
164523										END orbit 1
164523					FL250			6° F		start orbit 2
164824					FL250			6° F		end orbit 2
164824					FL250			6° F		start orbit 3
165129								6° F		end 3
165129					FL250			6° F		start 4
165430										end 4
165524	165504					45° AOB		6° F		start orbit 5
165564b										end 5
16564b								6° F		start 6
165819										end 6
165819								6° F		start 7
170020										end 7
170020								6° F		start 8
170143										end 8
170400					FL250	'		0°		
170440										start profile 3
171345										FL250 → 320
171345										end profile
171345					FLB 320			0°		start run 4.1
171600					320			180°		
171753										end 4.1
171930					FL 320					start run 4.2
172130					FL 320			0°		
172435										end 4.2
172515								98° A		start 4.3
173000										end 4.3
173145					DL 320			180°		start 4.4
173547										end 4.4
173838					FL 320			0°		start run 5
174345								180°		
174400								0°		SWITCH TO 0°
175400								180°		SWITCH TO 180°
180000								0°		Turn to 0°

Flight Manager's Instrument Status Log

Flight No. **B...040**.....

Date **20.8.04**.....

Instrument	Fitted	Operated	Instrument	Fitted	Operated
<u>Navigation</u>			<u>Cloud Physics</u>		
INU			<u>Probes</u>		
GPS		✓	FFSSP		✓
Satcom C			PCASP		
Satcom H		✓	2D-P	✗	
<u>Thermometers</u>			2D-C	✗	
De-Iced Temp			Cloudscope	✗	
Non De-Iced		✓	SID 1		✓
Heimann		✓	SID 2	✗	
<u>Hygrometers</u>			CPI	✗	
G. Eastern		✓	HVPS	✗	
J. Williams			<u>Racks:</u>		
Nevzorov	✗		INC	✗	
TWC		✓	CCN / CNC		✓
FWVS		✓	CVI		✓
<u>Radiometers</u>			<u>Aerosol</u>		
Upper Clear			PSAP		✓
“ Red		✓	Nephelometer		✓
“ Silicon			AMS	✓	✗
“ JO1D		✓			
Lower Clear					
“ Red		✓			
“ Silicon					
“ JO1D		✓			
<u>Large Radiometers</u>					
TAFTS	✗				
MARSS	✗				
DEIMOS	✗				
ARIES					
SWS / SHIM		✓			
<u>Chemistry</u>					
Ozone		✓			
ECGC					
NOX					
CO		✓	<u>Others:</u>		
ORAC	✗				
PAN					
PERCA					
WAS					

Flight Manager's Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. 6040

Instruments

1. ~~Pass~~^{SWS} Rack Intercom box, 1 side can't hear ch 2, stbd side
2. RFC - no picture
3. Ozone - reading - 11 ppb after t/0 ←
4. Neph - pressure signal noisy and offset
Neph 788mb, Static 696mb @ FL100.
5. Radalt - reading ~~off~~^{t/a} (65534 DRSU) [after ramping to 500ppb.]
6. UFC / DFC - both frozen over after t/0, UFC cleared @ 1336
7. Upper Red BBR - noisy on into Sun leg jumping btwn. 295 + 260 Wm⁻² then settled down to normal.
8. 1535 TWC status light flashing after start of P2 then stayed on
all paras = 2046 DRSU except 78 Status = 3947. Sw off / on.
2045
2044
173 EVIC = 65408
174 EV2C = 65408
- 1609 - reset PAFT DLU, caused spike in car con DLU data
(DI + NDI from -42 to -33°), recovered when PAFT CB made
9. F.M. display locked up @ 1632 when selecting on Fltsum panel
reset pc

Aircraft

B040 20-Aug-04 15:49:31 000 (11:03:31) 57.79 1.5

Event mark

- 37.RDHT
- 70.TWCD
- 71.TNOS
- 72.TSAM
- 73.TAMB
- 74.TSRC
- 75.HTR1
- 78.STAT

4094	65534
2046	2046
2046	2046
2046	2046

2046	2046
2046	2046
2046	2046
0947	0947

75.TWC EVAP1 CURRNT
 76.TWC EVAP2 CURRNT
 77.TWC SRCE CURRNT
 78.TWC STATUS WORD
 04.HDR VIC CLR C/C

B040 20-Aug-04 15:49:58 000 (11:03:31) 57.78 1.6

Event mark

- 37.RDHT
- 70.TWCD
- 71.TNOS
- 72.TSAM
- 73.TAMB
- 74.TSRC
- 75.HTR1
- 78.STAT

4094	65534
2046	2046
2045	2045
2046	2046

2046	2046
2046	2046
2045	2045
3947	3947

75.TWC EVAP1 CURRNT
76.TWC EVAP2 CURRNT
77.TWC SRCE CURRNT
78.TWC STATUS WORD
81.HDR VIO CURRNT

New plot, same times

Flight B040 16:13:12

Heading 252 deg Speed 332 knots Height 31.8kft Press 276mb

Lat 57.8N Long 0.4E Wind 29 ms-1/ 230 deg

Temp -50.82C Dewpoint -48.14C

From 15:40:59 to now

Current values

—	TIME FROM MIDNIGHT	58392	secs	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> All
—	DEICED TRUE AIR TEMP	-50.82	deg C	<input type="checkbox"/>
—	NONDEICED TRUE AIR TEMP	-51.44	deg C	<input type="checkbox"/>

New plot, same times

Flight B040 16:10:33

Heading 249 deg Speed 326 knots Height 30.2kft Press 297mb

Lat 57.6N Long 0.7E Wind 30 ms-1/ 230 deg

Temp -47.24C Dewpoint -47.31C

From 15:10:06 to now

Current values

TIME FROM MIDNIGHT

58233 secs

All

— DEICED TRUE AIR TEMP

-47.25 deg C

C

- - - NONDEICED TRUE AIR TEMP

-47.87 deg C

C

New plot, same times

Flight B040 14:47:07

Heading 230 deg Speed 354 knots Height 31.9kft Press 274mb

Lat 58.0N Long 0.5E Wind 30 ms-1/ 222 deg

Temp -51.03C Dewpoint -52.48C

From 13:46:13 to now

Current values

	TIME FROM MIDNIGHT	53226	secs	Ⓒ All
—	UPPER PYRANOMETER CLEAR FLUX	465.23	W m-2	⌋
—	UPPER PYRANOMETER RED FLUX	258.1	W m-2	⌋
—	LOWER PYRANOMETER CLEAR FLUX	188.23	W m-2	⌋
—	LOWER PYRANOMETER RED FLUX	72.99	W m-2	⌋

New plot, same times

Flight B040 17:33:48

Heading 192 deg Speed 297 knots Height 9.7kft Press 704mb

Lat 52.6N Long 0.4W Wind 7 ms-1/ 253 deg

Temp -0.08C Dewpoint -3.44C

From 13:38:27 to 14:08:30

Current values
 TIME FROM MIDNIGHT
 NEPH PRESSURE

63228 secs
 -6.76 mb

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